

INTEGRATIVE OMICS

ELIXIR IT-All Hands Meeting
Rome, November 27th, 2023

Dr.ssa Ylenia Antonacci
Tecnologo CNR-IBIOM
y.antonacci@ibiom.cnr.it

What about CNR BiOmics?

Automated liquid handling systems

Single-cell molecular analysis platforms

PacBio Sequel

Illumina NovaSeq 6000

HIGH-QUALITY and HIGH-THROUGHPUT massively sequencing platforms

Oxford Nanopore GridION

CNR.BiOmics

BIG DATA FOR BETTER LIFE

Complementary platforms for NGS technologies

BioNano Genomics

ICT Facility 10K core – 15 Pb

Metabolomics and Proteomics Platforms

Orbitrap Fusion™ nLC-MS LTQ XL

Genomic and transcriptomic data validation platforms

Genetic Analyzer 3500DX

QuantStudio™ 12K Flex

The CNRBIOmics project allowed the establishment in ELIXIR-IT of a Platform for “Integrative Omics” providing the user community with state of the art equipment for high-throughput generation of genomic, proteomic and metabolomic data.

CNR.BiOmics

BIG DATA FOR BETTER LIFE

NextGenIT

Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

What about ELIXIRxNextGenIT?

AIM OF THE PROJECT:

WP 3 - Empowering the ELIXIR-IT Integrative Omics Infrastructure
(GENOMIC Platform, Dr. A. Tullo: IBIOM-CNR; ITB MI-CNR; UNIBA- DBBA)

Emerging technologies

Sequencing platforms with high and medium throughput

Illumina
NovaSeq X

Illumina NextSeq
2000

Oxford Nanopore
GridION

✓ DNA Methylation

✓ Analysis, concentration and EVs Count

✓ Spatial Transcriptomics

✓ SingleCell Analysis

Work in progress of infrastructure:

✓ Spatial Transcriptomics

10X Genomics **CytAssist**

✓ Announcement of tenders already published

✓ Analysis, concentration and EVs Count and virus-like particles

Multilaser Nanoparticle
Tracking Analysis - **NTA**

Work in progress of infrastructure:

✓ Spatial Transcriptomics

10X Genomics **CytAssist**

✓ Analysis, concentration and EVs Count and virus-like particles

Multilaser Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis - **NTA**

✓ Announcement of tenders already published

✓ STAFF RECRUITMENT with high experience

Genomic Services on demand

**WHOLE
GENOME SEQ
(WGS)**

METAGENOMICS

**GENOME WIDE
OPTICAL MAPPING**

**TARGET
ENRICHMENT**

**TRANSCRIPTOME
SEQUENCING**
Total RNA-seq, mRNA-seq,
small RNA-seq

**GENOMIC VALIDATION
OF TRANSCRIPTOMICS
data**

**EPIGENETIC
ANALYSIS**

Single cell OMICS

Industries Service on demand

Analysis for optimizing processes, products, quality tests in agri-food, environmental, biomedical and veterinary

- Identification of clinical biomarkers
- Identification of active ingredients and evaluation of therapeutic effects

Contaminants identification

Molecular analysis of environmental samples

"OMICS" in healthcare practice (e.g. patient stratification for precision therapies)

Services already provided for Industry or companies

Metagenomic analysis of microbiomes associated with the rhizosphere and fruits for the identification of intervention approaches for reducing the effect of pathogens

Control test for bacterial contamination in drugs

Microbiome analysis from human feces for personalized prebiotic prescription

Microbiomes analysis from animal feces for the development of processes and products for veterinary use

Metagenomic analysis to study changes in relation to use of different treatments, in order to reduce the use of pesticides

Collaborations and services already provided for Governmental Institution and Foundations

FONDAZIONE

SANTA LUCIA
NEUROSCIENZE
E RIABILITAZIONE

Platform Strengths:

High expertise and multidisciplinary skills thanks to integration with other platforms

Complementarity of sequencing technologies

Storage of omics-data for a medium-long time

Customization and consultancy support both upstream (sample management) and downstream (resolution of unexpected problems)

PANDEMIC PERIOD: Covid-19

About us

European Portal

Support & Feedback

Search

en

it

Genomics & Transcriptomics Protein Data Imaging Data Health Data

Research Events

Accelerating research through data sharing

The Italian COVID-19 Data Portal provides information, guidelines, tools and services to support researchers in creating and sharing research data on COVID-19.

The portal is developed as part of a federative European initiative promoted by [EMBL-EBI](#) based on the [European COVID-19 Data Portal](#) and national portals.

If you are producing or working with COVID-19 data and have any questions about sharing and managing your data, please feel free to get in touch with us.

This resource is developed by [ELIXIR-IT](#) in collaboration with CNR, GARR and ISS.

This portal is a collaborative effort and most of the pages on this website are manually curated.

Contact us at covid19.helpdesk@lists.covid19dataportal.it to report errors or inaccuracies. Your help is really appreciated!

Highlights

Latest published highlights. [See all highlights.](#)

Tweets by @elixir_it

ELIXIR Italy Retweeted

Consortium GARR @ReteGARR

SAVE THE DATE! Il 6 maggio torna l' #opensciencecafé 🍷. Parleremo di #copyright nella ricerca scientifica con il prof. Roberto Cippitani dell' @UniperugiaNews Vi aspettiamo! Per registrarsi all'evento ➡ learning.garr.it

[Embed](#) [View on Twitter](#)

Institutional Resources

communications biology

ARTICLE

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-023-04784-4> OPEN

Check for updates

HaploCoV: unsupervised classification and rapid detection of novel emerging variants of SARS-CoV-2

Matteo Chiara^{1,2}, David S. Horner^{1,2}, Erika Ferrandi^{1,2}, Carmela Gissi^{2,3} & Graziano Pesole^{2,3}

Comparative analysis of >12M SARS-Cov-2 genomes to prioritize “dangerous” variants

INVOLVEMENT OF ELIXIR-IT IN «GENOMES of EUROPE»

The Genome of Europe initiative aims to build a European network of national genomic reference cohorts of at least 500,000 citizens. These reference cohorts will be selected to be representative of the European population.

To achieve this, each country involved will establish a population cohort that reflects the genetic composition of its population, including both healthy and diseased individuals. The country will then connect this data into a European cohort, thus establishing a collective European reference dataset.

The 500,000 sequenced genomes collected will contribute to the million genomes aimed for in the 1+MG initiative.

European commitment to achieve access to at least 1 million sequenced genomes by 2022

B1MG is creating legal guidance, best practices, recommendations and an infrastructure to achieve the goal

2 SEQUENCING FACILITIES FOR ITALY

A GENOME DATA INFRASTRUCTURE FOR PRECISION MEDICINE

European Genomic Data Infrastructure

ELIXIR coordinates the GDI project (Horizon Europe Call: DIGITAL-2021-CLOUD-AI-01, start 1 Nov 2022, €40,000,000) involving 22 countries including Italy.

Genomic Data are a critical part of Health Big Data toward Precision Medicine practices. On the 10th April 2018 the declaration: *"Towards access of at least 1 million sequenced Genomes in the EU by 2022"* was signed by 13 EU member states and the '1+ Million Genomes' initiative (1+MG) was formed as a multi-country project. The 1+MG initiative aims to build a trust framework for the effective and secure cross-border access to repositories of personal genomic datasets among participating countries.

A federated data infrastructure (**Federated European Genome Phenome Archive**) is being designed to safeguard that national genomic data collections will be stored safely in the respective countries, and will be made accessible for collective analysis across borders rather than being collected in a central European repository. GDI covers collective agreements on ELSI aspects such as GDPR-compliance and personal consenting by participating citizens, what standards and minimal clinical phenotype to include, and quality criteria to perform genome sequencing.

WP3 INTEGRATIVE OMICS PLATFORM

Genomic UNIT

STAFF OVERVIEW

Dr. Elisabetta
Sbisà,
CNRBIomics&
WP LEADER

Dr. Apollonia
Tullo,
WP3 LEADER
and **SCIENTIFIC**
RESPONSIBLE
OF GENOMIC
UNIT

Dr. Flaviana
Marzano,
RESEARCHER

Dr. Daniela
Isabel
Abbrescia,
TECHNOLOGIST

Dr.
ChrysoValentinos
Pousis,
TECHNOLOGIST

Dr. Ylenia
Antonacci
TECHNOLOGIST

nextGenIT

*Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics*

THANKS